

D4.12 Instructions for final reporting of Joint Integrative Projects

Workpackage 4

Responsible Partner: SVA

Contributing partners: Sciensano, INSA

GENERAL INFORMATION

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INSTRUCTIONS FOR FINAL REPORTING OF JOINT INTEGRATIVE PROJECTS

Purpose

The purpose of these guidelines is to support Project Leaders (PLs) in the preparation of their final project reports. In addition to the information provided by PLs in these final reports, WP4 will collect information from OHEJP partners in order to assess how the project outputs have been taken on board in OHEJP partner organisations; both awareness of the outputs, its relevance to the organisation and the level of actual implementation.

Both the final reports and the integrative assessment will be submitted to an external evaluation, which will focus on assessing the existing or possible impact of the project on the prioritised objectives defined in the SRA (WP2) and by stakeholders (WP5). The context in which the final report is framed is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Context in which final reports of Joint Integrative Projects are written and evaluated.

The results of the evaluation will be reported to the OHEJP PMT and also used by WP7 to support activities aimed at future sustainability of the developed collaborative structures. The achievements will also be reported back to the Stakeholders' Committee and to the Research Executive Agency.

The final reports will also be used to report on JIP progress in general, and be submitted to the OHEJP Coordinator who will produce Summary Progress Reports and Periodic Annual Reports that are official deliverables of the One Health EJP programme.

Please note that these reports should only cover scientific and technical issues. Financial progress will be reported by each beneficiary and will comprise all their respective activities, e.g. involvement in JRPs, JIPs, education & training activities as well as overarching EJP tasks. The financial reporting is not covered by this procedure.

These instructions cover only the final reporting. Instructions for periodic reporting are covered in Deliverable D4.1, which was released in 2018. The latest version of all guidelines can be found on the OHEJP website.

1. Planning of the reporting

The timing for final reporting on JIPs, and for the external evaluation, is provided in Figure 2. As a general rule, the final report should be submitted within 2 months after the project has finished. This means that for 1st round projects, the final report will be due some time between February and August 2021, depending on whether an extension is asked for and for how long. For 2nd round projects, the deadline for the final report is August 2022.

2. Reporting process

The process for final reporting is shown in figure 3. Two months after the end of their JIP, project leaders shall submit their final report to WP4. These reports will serve to draft the annual EJP report by the Steering Team and WP1, but will also be evaluated by external evaluators who are recognised experts, independent of the One Health EJP partners and representing a stakeholder perspective. They have 3 months for conducting their evaluations, after which the reports will be submitted to the SSB for discussion. Furthermore, the annual ethics report will use information from this final report.

WP4 will send the project leaders the appropriate template for reporting.

Similar to the annual periodic report, the template for the final report will include:

- Work carried out, scientific results (5000 words, 10 pages);
- Summary of the work carried out (500 words, 1 page);
- Achievement of the project: milestones and deliverables (tables);
- Publications and patents, if any;
- Expected impact in terms of closing the gap between Med and Vet, what results have been obtained regarding integration (e.g. databases, protocols, ...) and harmonisation of procedures and other approaches;
- Follow-up of the recommendations identified by the Ethics Advisors: explaining the actions and measures that have been taken to comply with these.
- Summary of dissemination and Communication activities.

The final One Health EJP reports and external evaluation reports will in the end be submitted to the External Scientific Advisory Board. The reports will also serve as an input for WP5 (Science to policy) and WP7 (Sustainability).

Figure 3. The destination and use of information from final reports of Joint Integrative Project.

3. Scientific Steering Board (SSB)

The final reports will be discussed at the next SSB meeting after their submission, in February or in September each year. In general, no presentations by PLs are foreseen at these meetings, but PLs may be invited to present and comment on the final report of their JIP. To this end, PLs may also propose to be heard by the SSB.

4. Contents of final project report

The final report should contain the following elements:

4.1. 1. Work carried out, scientific results

5000 words, 10 pages. Describe all tasks per project work package

4.2. 2. Summary of the work carried out

500 words, 1 page

4.3. 3. Achievements of the project: milestones and deliverables

JIP name	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes / No)	Comments

And

JIP name	Project deliverable number	Deliverable name	Delivery date from AWP	Actual delivery date	Comments

4.4. 4. Publications and patents

List all peer reviewed publications (please mention if these are registered in OpenAIRE) and others, including the doi reference, if available.

If no doi reference is available (e.g. article in journal, publication in conference proceedings or workshop, book or monograph, chapter in a book, thesis/Dissertation, other), please provide as much information as possible. The One Health EJP might contact you for further instructions.

4.5. 5. One Health impact

Expected impacts in terms of:

- closing the gap between Med and Vet,
- integration of new partners in the project during its runtime
- extension activities aimed at integration
- what specific results have been obtained regarding integration (e.g. databases, protocols, ...) and harmonisation of procedures and other approaches

4.6. 6. Follow-up of the recommendations and comments in previous review(s) by the Ethics Advisors

Please list the recommendations that you received from the Ethics Advisors and clearly explain the actions and measures that have been taken to comply with these.

4.7. 7. Summary of dissemination and communication activities

Based on data recorded as described below (form available on OHEJP website), please summarise the dissemination and communication activities conducted by the JIP over its runtime.

Name of the event:			
Date:			
Place:			
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
		Yes / No	Yes / No
	Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference
	Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop

<i>Press release</i>		<i>Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop</i>	
<i>Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)</i>		<i>Video/Film</i>	
<i>Exhibition</i>		<i>Brokerage Event</i>	
<i>Flyer</i>		<i>Pitch Event</i>	
<i>Training</i>		<i>Trade Fair</i>	
<i>Social Media</i>		<i>Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects</i>	
<i>Website</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)</i>			
<i>Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories</i>			
	<i>Number</i>		<i>Number</i>
<i>Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)</i>		<i>Media</i>	
<i>Industry</i>		<i>Investors</i>	
<i>Civil Society</i>		<i>Customers</i>	
<i>General Public</i>		<i>Other</i>	
<i>Policy Makers</i>			